

Curriculum Pathways and Vocational/Technical Competency-Based Education for Achieving Sustainable Development Goals in Education

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Abstract

One of the United Nations' priorities to be achieved by 2030 are Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) using education as a core instrument. Also, Competency-Based Education (CBE) remains an innovative approach to attain a measurable level of competency in the process of pursuing the actualisation of the SDGs. However observations from public discourse reveals criticisms on the interpretation of competency-based education in curriculum practice. On this premise, the paper discussed "curriculum pathways and vocational/technical competency-based education for achieving sustainable development goals in education". A review of the concept of sustainable development, SDG 1 and curriculum pathways was done with conceptual clarification of Competency-Based Education and an appraisal of its theoretical foundations to clear ambiguities, and for its practical relevance. Vocational and Technical Education Curriculum Pathways (VTECP) where competency-based education approaches are central for adequate knowledge and skills acquisition for employment and sustainability was also examined... As a pathway to achieve sustainable development goals, the significant position of criterion-reference assessment for learners to be vocationally competent were lucidly presented. It is recommended that the use of demonstrable pedagogy and the pre-eminence of standardized competency in skills acquisition should be made paramount in the education process for sustainable development vision to be achieved.

Key words: Competency-based education, Curriculum pathways, Sustainable development goals, Vocational/Technical education

Word count: 200

Background

In the contemporary world, several countries and regions at various times had often converged to discuss education matters through diverse agendas of values from different and contextual perspectives for global relevance. Specifically, among those global agendas centred on education include innovations in education, digitalisation, entrepreneurship, globalisation/internationalization, education in emergencies, and sustainable development as often reflects in several curriculum reforms from cultural and environmental perspectives. International interactions among world leaders, therefore, through global forum for addressing issues that transcend national boundaries, aim at offering collective solutions and advance development of the participating nations. It implies that in the process, attention is often drawn to several aspects of education and its hub, that is, the curriculum through which the educational priorities of nations are implemented and achieved.

In specific term, education itself is a goal, and simultaneously, it has a cross-cutting roles across all the 17 Sustainable Development Goals(SDGs).The core goal of education is *quality education(SDG 4)* That is, the goal which aims at "ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all" by 2030. The SDG 4 covers every stage of the learning process, namely, Free primary and secondary education for all boys and girls by 2030;Early childhood development fostering quality pre-primary education and child care; Technical and vocational training which is expected to be affordable and accessible for all genders; Eliminate gender and wealth disparities in education outcomes at all levels; universal youth literacy and numeracy by ensuring foundational skills acquisition ;and Education for Sustainable Development(ESD) which is expected to be the driver of societal transformation through worthwhile knowledge, skills acquisition and values which school curricula should anchor.

One of its vast array of activities aimed at improving people's lives globally is education for sustainable development. Education for sustainable development(ESD) aims at developing competencies that empower individuals to reflect on their own actions, taking into account their current and future social, cultural, economic, and environmental impacts, from a local and a global perspective(Cebrián,Junyent.& Mulà,2020).It is further reiterated that ESD has to be understood as an integral part of quality education, inherent in the concept of lifelong learning whereby all educational institutions, from preschool to higher education, and in non-formal and informal education can and should foster the development of sustainability competencies. Arising from the education agenda 2030 target of the United Nations, curriculum, through various subject and programme specialisations becomes the pathway(s) for achieving the proficient competencies needed for sustainable development.

However, for educational curricula to yield a sustainable society, a relatively diverse perspectives have emerged among education stakeholders regarding the place of Competency-Based education (CBE) which should be fostered through diverse curricula in the theory and practice of education. Although, some quarters use the term Competency-Based Approach (CBA), the issue is not with the nomenclature, but human perceptions of CBE/CBA which has implications for curricula practices in the education process. Despite its merits, the competency-based approach (CBA) has faced criticism from Western academics and educationalists (Preston, J2017).Conceptually, competency is composed primarily of knowledge, skills and demonstrable behaviour. According to (Boukhentache, (2020) in respect of teaching Language skills, the concept of competency refers to the ability to integrate language knowledge and language skills with social skills to use English aptly in various real-life situations. Still, a substantial body of literature presents criticisms of competency-based education, the most significant being the imprecision and ambiguity of competence definitions (Mirza, Teymoori and Mizza (2023),

In addition, the writer's observation in contemporary times is that arguments persist on the correlation between competence in knowledge acquisition, skills and performance. In order to shed more light on the subject matter of Competency-Based Education(CBE) therefore, and to clear ambiguities in its interpretation for practical relevance in respect of curriculum pathways, and Competency-Based education(CBE),from vocational/technical curriculum implementation perspectives, ,all for achieving the core goal of education for sustainable development of individuals and the society at large ,this theoretical paper was conceived and the subject matter lucidly explored. The author of this paper also philosophically hypothesised in conception that the lack of a clear conceptualization and definition of the term competency within the operational framework of Competency-Based Education (CBE) remains an issue of public debate, and it continues to adversely affect teachers' understanding of this initiative development in education , and subsequently, it is very much likely to affect its implementation in African countries and

elsewhere if not operationally explored. Besides, the inherent contributions of the areas examined in this theoretical paper, the subject matter would equally give vocational-based curriculum its rightful place in curriculum matters, and ensure that measurable activities that would practically promote and develop competencies that empower individuals in a sustainable manner are fostered in curriculum theory and practice.

Curriculum Pathway(s) as a Central Hub of Education for Sustainable development

Global education is recognised as a fundamental human right and a powerful driver for poverty eradication, social justice, peace, and sustainable development, and this recognition extends beyond formal schooling to encompass all stages of life. Nonetheless, curriculum remains the engine that pilots the societal values to be achieved through the process of educating the citizenry of any nation of the world. Curriculum is the hearth beat of education which anchors the educational priorities of any society. The curriculum acts as a central "hub" within the global education agenda of education for Sustainable Development. The SDG 4 on Quality Education is , to equip learners with the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes needed to address global challenges and promote a sustainable future(Osman, Ladhani,Findlater & McKay,2017). This involves transforming curriculum objectives, content, learning activities, pedagogical approaches and evaluation techniques to foster education for sustainable development with proficient competences of the recipients.

However, there is a panoply of definitions of the concept of sustainable development, but the most widely accepted being that of the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED): which defines sustainable development as "a model of development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (Makhrouf& Ait Hbib, 2023). This definition underlines the concept of needs, which must be given the highest priority in order to meet the needs of future generations and the responsibility of present generations to protect the interests of future generations. The needs can only be met through the curriculum pathways in respective educational institutions while it is the responsibility of the education stakeholders and experts to constantly reform the respective curriculum pathways and implement such adequately. The results would be a transformed education that breeds school leavers prepared for the world of work and sustainable living.

According to United States Department of Education (2020), curriculum pathways for success refers to structured educational programmes and sequences of courses designed to guide students toward achieving their academic, career, and personal goals, often with flexibility and options to cater for individual needs and aspirations. These curriculum pathways emphasize a clear sequence of curriculum components and competencies required for specific credentials and or successful transitions to higher education or the workforce, incorporating saleable skills, specialized subjects, and real-industrial practical experiences that align with the curriculum pathways. Since one of the targets of SDG 4 specifically calls for ensuring that all learners acquire knowledge and skills for sustainable development, including education for sustainable development (ESD), human rights, gender equality, and global citizenship, the need arises in this paper to further reposition the expectations of the formal curriculum pathways in vocational/technical education within the context of Competency-Based Education approach to build a sustainable society.

On the basis that there is no formal education programmes and subjects that have no curriculum which anchors its components, the identified pathways in this paper are “Academic Pathway, Subject-Specific Pathways and Vocational Pathways appraised as follows.

Academic Pathways: - These refer to educational steps and or programmes through which an individual achieve academic goal(s), career prospect, and mostly academic knowledge attainment. Such certification acquired as an academic success include a diploma certificate, degree and a medium or short course certificate. Each Academic Pathway has specific list of courses in the order that they should be taken by learners. In another perspective, from St’Petersburge College homepage (2024), academic pathways serve as the academic plan for you to use when planning for your college degree. Although, an individual will have some choice in terms of options, they have been designed to build the knowledge and skills that will result in higher academic achievement and are often called ‘stackable’ certificates. These pathways provide a clear roadmap for navigating coursework or programmes and achieving desired outcomes like a degree, certificate, transfer to a higher education institution, or entry into the world of work. The fact remains that an academic pathway, as an academic plan and as the programme itself is expected to prepare individuals undergoing any programme for the world of work, but it becomes worrisome when the academic pathways are full of academic varieties at the expense of skills needed for sustainable development.

Subject-Specific Pathways: These are structured progression of specialised academic discipline with formal training experiences designed to develop expertise in specific institutional subject or course of study. Subject-specific pathways are structured educational routes or programmes designed to guide students towards a particular field of study or career, often involving specialised courses, qualifications, or vocational training (University of Passau, Information Book, 2025). Through subject-specific pathways, individual learners who meet the requirements acquire subject-specific knowledge and skills, and can further advance in the knowledge and skills acquired. Examples of subject-specific pathways include Language pathways; English, French, Spanish, etc.; Artspaths: Theatre Arts, Music, Visual Arts, etc.; Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) pathways; Health science pathways –Public health, Medicine, Nursing, etc. and ; Vocational and technical education pathways which is a focus in this context is further discussed subsequently in this paper. In contrast to a more generalized curricula, subject-specific pathways through the curriculum of each are structured around a subject’s core concepts and applications, often linking to real-world of work relevance, functionality and for economic sustainability. However, the depth of expertise or competency of learners in their chosen subject-specific pathway in preparing them for sustainable development through various curriculum implementation plans and strategies remain a concern for the stakeholders of education. This observation further consolidates the specific viewpoints explored in this theoretical paper.

Theoretical Foundations of Competency-Based Education (TFCBE)

Competency-Based Education has basis in a number of available theories in educational literature, and the philosophy behind such theories provides the foundation on which Competency-Based Education (CBE) must be built in the theory and practice of education for sustainable development. In mastery learning theory of Benjamin Bloom in 1968, the core idea is *“If you give learners enough time plus the right instruction, almost everyone can master a competency”*. It implies that the competency expected is mastery. This works when there is or are measurable objectives upon which a teacher teaches and determine a percentage level of performance, say 70% and above as a standard of mastery while any demonstrable performance below the score gives more time and opportunity for the learners to relearn to master the subject matter. Skinner Gagne behaviourist learning theory also presented learning observable behaviours which can be measured and reinforce for competency to be achieved. The impression of Gagne’s core idea is that instructional events to be measured in the process of education must be guided by enabling and measurable

objectives which are needed for skill acquisition and mastery for any learner to be regarded competent in a specific task or performance.

In addition, the core idea of Albert Bandura is that *“People learn by observing others and by self-efficacy”*. In this respect, learners’ modelling their tutors or mentors with their belief in the ability to do it to a measurable level of mastery is in agreement with competency-based education. The Outcomes-Based Education (OBE) of Spedy in 1994 also established that the desired exit outcome of teaching in the instructional process must be designed, and learners must be able to perform the task to the standard designed in the instructional process. Similarly, the core idea of constructivist theory of Piaget, Vygotsky affirmed that *“learners build knowledge by doing and reflecting, not by passively receiving”*. The constructivist philosophy underlies CBE, emphasizing student autonomy and meaningful application of skills in authentic contexts (.McGuire, 2024). On the whole, as appraised from the existing theories, it is ideal for demonstrable competency-based education practices to be measured based on standard or agreed level of mastery to produce functional manpower for a sustainable society. Competency-Based Education (CBE) therefore is a pedagogical approach that prioritizes the demonstration of mastery over time-based on seat time. It emphasizes learning outcomes, enabling students to progress after proving they have acquired specific skills, knowledge, and behaviours (Study com, 2024, online platform). It becomes very significant that the curriculum pathways in educational institutions in Africa and beyond, including vocational/technical education must have footings in the philosophical lens appraised for achieving sustainable development goals in education.

Vocational / Technical Education and Competency-Based Education

The broadfield of Vocational and Technical Education (VTE) covers a myriad of skilled-based and specialised curriculum pathways with hands-on skills activities and related knowledge involved in the educational programmes. It is designed for learners to acquire knowledge, skills and competencies specific to a particular occupation or trade or class of occupation. Vocational education may have work-based components like apprenticeship. Successful completion of such programmes is expected to lead to labour-market needs. Vocational education, also known as vocational training or vocational education and training (VET), is a form of education that prepares individuals for specific trades, occupations, or vocations by providing them with the necessary skills, knowledge, and competencies for a particular job, or career+ (UNESCO Institute of Statistics, 2025). Vocational education is effective when a student, upon completing their studies, is capable of becoming self-sufficient and financially independent (Olowe, 2023). Technical education is a form of education that equip learners with vocational skills and knowledge in various fields.

The comprehensive term which is an embodiment of vocational and technical skills for job success is vocational and technical education. Vocational and Technical Education refers to the branch of education that facilitates the learning of practical and applied skills, together with fundamental scientific knowledge (Ikpe, 2010). Vocational and Technical Education is a form of learning that focuses on acquiring practical and applicable skills, as well as fundamental scientific information (Olowe, 2023).. Vocational education focuses on preparing individuals for specific occupations and trades through hands-on training and practical skills, while technical education emphasizes the scientific and theoretical underpinnings of specific technical fields.

Similarly, technical education often involves more in depth academic knowledge added to the hands-on skills practices. Still, both vocational and technical education are forms of career-focused education aimed at immediate employment for job-placement, self-reliance and sustainable development, but differ in their emphasis and scope of what they pass on to the trainees or learners. According to UNESCO(2011),the acronym, TVET is used to be an embracing term for vocational-based programmes .and it refers to Technical and Vocational Education and Training(TVET) which

implies all forms and levels of education which provide knowledge and skills related to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life through formal, non-formal and informal learning methods in both school-based and work-based learning contexts. Technical and Vocational Education and training (TVET) focuses on the learning and mastery of specialized techniques and the scientific principles underlying those techniques, as well as general knowledge, skills and values, UNESCO report recorded.

The values inherent in Technical and Vocational Education and training (TVET) in theory and practice cannot be maximally explored without adopting the core principles of Competency-Based Education. As rightly put by McGuire (2022) that the demonstration of mastery learning and application of skills in different contexts is prioritized in Competency-Based Education, TVET is skill-based, and the employability skills in TVET must be acquired by learners with a high degree or measure of competency Dhlamini, Bhebhe, and Dlamini (2018) asserted that Competency-Based Education is concerned with inculcation of basic competencies seen to be appropriate for society. UNESCO-UNEVOC International Centre for Technical and Vocational Education and Training established in 2020 also conceptualised Competency-based education (CBE) as education built on the philosophy that "almost all learners can learn equally well if they receive the kind of instructors they need". In the, UNESCO-UNEVOC report, CBE places a new and systematic emphasis on this principle. It is inferred therefore by the author of this paper as adapted from the UNESCO document, that the systematic development and delivery of the training to learners in any case to achieve competency-based education should be guided by five essential elements thus:

- (i) The tasks to be taught should be identified by the experts in the field, eg, TVET field.
- (ii) The curriculum pathways should allow each learner to have the opportunity to develop and to be evaluated on the measures of the competencies achieved.
- (iii) Assessment of competency is not only based on knowledge acquisition and attitude but primarily on the actual demonstration of the competency of the skills acquired.
- (iv) A specific measure of standards or a determined proficiency level should be used as the basis for assessing learning outcomes in the curriculum pathways enshrined in educational institutions, and learners/trainees should be aware of them as the expected target in the learning and the training process.
- (v) The Learners/trainees' progress reports and the overall evaluation results should always have separate specific skills competencies measured 'added to the knowledge-based results of the learners in the programme as a true resemblance that competency-based assessment is captured and attained in their education process.

In the same vein, Competency-Based Education well captured in conception and practice is beyond traditional content delivery approach in equipping learners with the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes necessary to make informed decisions and be functional in the society Vocational and Technical Education Curriculum Pathways (VTECP) where competency-based education in policy and in implementation approaches should be fostered among other subject-specific or programme specific pathways for employment need and sustainable development include the list below among many others. Also included are most of the sellable and the employability skills needed for the world of work.

Table 1: Vocational and Technical Education Curriculum Pathways (VTECP) and Skills Needed for the Labour Market

Vocational and Technical Education Curriculum Pathways (VTECP)	Skills Needed for the Labour Market
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automotive:- <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automotive technician. - Diesel mechanic. - Auto body repair. - Auto electrical works • Air conditioning and Refrigeration • Block laying, brick laying and concrete works • Beauty and Wellness:- <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cosmetology (hairdressing, styling) - Aesthetics (skincare) - Barbering • Cosmetology <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nail technology • Catering craft servicing • Clothing and textiles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Garment making <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dyeing and bleaching • Construction:- <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Carpentry and joinery - Furniture making - Upholstery -Machine woodworking - Electrical installation and maintenance work -Electronics -Radio,TV,and Electronic servicing - Plumbing and Pipefitting - Masonry - Painting and decorating. • Culinary:- <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chef - Baker - Pastry chef • Health Care:- <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nursing assistant - Dental assistant - Medical assistant 	<p>Sellable Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job-specific*: Relevant to a particular job or industry. • Technical*: Require specialized knowledge or training. • Valuable*: Highly sought after by employers. <p>Examples of sellable skills include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Programming languages (e.g., Python, Java) - Data analysis and visualization - Digital marketing (e.g., social media advertising) - Graphic design, etc. <p>Employability Skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transferable Relevant across various jobs and industries. • Soft skills focus on personal attributes, communication, and teamwork. • Essential*: Valued by employers for effective job performance. <p>Examples of employability skills include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication and teamwork - Problem-solving and critical thinking - Time management and organization - Adaptability and flexibility - Leadership and initiative

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information Technology:- <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Network administration - Cyber security - Database management - Web development • Engineering and Manufacturing:- <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Machining - Welding - Mechanical drafting • Energy and Utilities:- <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solar panel installation - Wind turbine maintenance - Electrical power line installation,etc • Welding and fabrication <p>➤ N.B.:A host of other vocational and technical education curriculum pathways and those offered on apprentice bases are available in various communities, local governments, locations, regions, states, and nations in the emerging society.</p>	
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As shown in table 1, a list of Vocational and Technical Education Curriculum Pathways and relevant corresponding sellable skills as well as employability skills needed for the labour market among others is identified. Sellable skills are specific, technical skills/expertise (job specific skills) that should be acquired by learners for the labour market needs in the contemporary times while employability skills are transferable skills that make an individual attractive to potential industrial /establishment employers. Examples of each are identified in table 1.

Criterion-Referencing Assessment and Learners’ Competency in Vocational and Technical Education

In vocational /technical competency-based education (VTCBE),the competency level of learners in tests, quiz, projects, practical skills acquisition and examination are expected to be determined using a range of statistical standards setting techniques and professional expertise to create the criteria which learners must meet. The approach of finding out if the candidates’ performance in the assessment and evaluation when measured using the standard assessment criteria to see if the skills acquisition or the passing standard is met is called criterion-referencing, and this is synonymous to mastery learning. Failure of learners/trainees to demonstrate the expected competence in the instructional process (formative), and at the end of the whole assessment of instruction (summative) irrespective of the percentage of performance implies that the expected competency level has not been met. The decision to continue repeating or demonstrating the tasks by the learner and the time frame in the school year, should usually be determined by the coordinating education ministry/ the professional body or the commission put in charge. Criterion-reference assessment used judiciously as part of the continuous teaching/learning process helps learners to see how and where they need to supplement their learning to meet the criteria (Renaissance Leadership, 2018).

As a practical example in measurement terms, if the level of competency (mastery) expected of a group of learners in the ability to perform the tasks involved in the final finishing of a furniture table top is **65%**, but assessment result of the competency level reached by some of the students is less than 65%, competency is regarded not to have been achieved by the students concerned. This illustration on competency-based education makes it understandable that even if majority of the students in a class gets above average in the performance of some identified tasks or activities, but gets less than say 65% as the criterion-percentage level set as competency score, they are not approved as proficient enough in the task(s) they have been assessed. Put together, the focus of competency-based education goes beyond just passing or getting an average score in the performance of a task, but high proficiency level of individual learners/trainees is the target for effective education in the 21st century.

Vocational/Technical Competency-Based Education (VTCBE) therefore is a progressive practical approach to vocational and technical education and training centred on what learners can do proficiently rather than how long they have been learning. The progression and proficiency fosters on mastery of defined competencies in the training, teaching and learning process. The vocational competency acquired becomes the demonstrable expertise and proficiency essential to perform specific job tasks in the chosen occupation competently. The dexterity or expertise to be demonstrated encompass practical application of knowledge, skills, and abilities in a real life situation in work places as industrial establishments or self-created job(s).

In both Competency –Based Education (CBE) and Vocational/Technical Competency-Based Education (VTCBE), demonstration of mastery of specific skills and knowledge rather than accumulating scores or marks got from bookish education full of academic varieties within a time frame is expected of the learners. Both CBE and VTCBE allow for individualized and guided learning paths and flexible pacing in practical terms which give learners the opportunity to learn at their own pace. As they advance, they demonstrate what they have learned and the competency level attained is assessed by the teacher with a frame of reference on the performance level of competency already set as a standard for the learners.

Towards Achieving Sustainable Development in Education through the curriculum pathways and competency-based education.

The nexus between curriculum pathways and vocational/technical competency-based education is crucial for developing a well-equipped, skilled and proficient workforce that would serve as instrument for sustainable development. In this dispensation of an increasing emphasis on aligning education through its curriculum with labour market needs using competency-based approaches, the time is ripe for relevant stakeholders to take workable actions with a view to achieving sustainable development goals using education as a launch pad. A call to action is made as follows as recommendations for relevant stakeholders to consider both in policy term and in curriculum implementation efforts.

- 1) **Integration of new skills and innovations in subject areas/curricula** -New skills ushered in as a result of knowledge explosion and innovations in subject areas/curricula and in other skills related to climate change, poverty reduction, gender equality, human rights, student agency, critical thinking, and the ability to act responsibly, which are crucial for addressing global challenges and cultural diversity-should be integrated or strengthened into each subject area using a Competency –Based approach in implementation.
- 2) **Teacher capacity building on Competency-Based Education** -Capacity of teachers in respective subject area of specialisation should be built on how to identify the specific skills in the subject matter of their specialisations as a guide to know the exact tasks to be performed

by learners, and the pedagogical approaches to ensure that learners would be able to demonstrate an appreciable competency level in each case.

- 3) **Resourced learning environment** -Professional teachers in the teaching field should be well supported with well-resourced learning environment for demonstrable activities to be possible for competency-based education to be practical-oriented.
- 4) **Learner engagement** -Learners should be engaged to competently acquire the skills in order to align with 21st century labour market demand needs.
- 5) **The ratio of practical to theory in lesson delivery** – The ratio of practical activities relevant to solve real-world problem should be more than theory--based teaching and learning –Ratio 60:40(Practical: Theory) may be given due consideration.
- 6) **Strengthening individualized learning approach** - Individualised learning approach should be encouraged for learners to acquire competency at their own pace.
- 7) **Enlightenment and access to vocational and technical education (VTE)** –The government should give more public enlightenment on the value inherent in vocational and technical education and strategize to improve access to vocational and technical education subjects and trades in the school curriculum in order to provide more future opportunities to learners from diverse background, interest and aptitude.
- 8) **Emphasis on skills acquisition and competency for learners’ promotion** –Skills acquisition and the competency performance level should carry a larger percentage as the determinant of learners’ promotion to the next class in their subject area compared with the theory acquired through a number of theoretical assignments within a period of time.
- 9) **Pre-eminence of skills competency for learners’ assessment**- Pre-eminence of learners’ assessment on their ability to demonstrate competence in a specific skill acquired through practical tasks should be prioritized over traditional grades, and a learner should be considered "competent" or "not yet competent" based on a measurable performance or proficiency level –A competency level/ standard (mastery) of 60% may be given due consideration by the appropriate ministry of education.
- 10) **Uses of demonstrable pedagogy in curriculum delivery** -Effective methods to be in use should include learner-cantered instruction, participatory projects, presentations, practical demonstration approach, team and project-based learning, experiential learning, outdoor education, and appropriate blend of formal and informal learning should be encouraged.
- 11) **Development and use of competency-based assessment tools** - The development of assessment tools to measure learners’ achievement in competency-based education by professional teachers and test and measurement/evaluation experts is very crucial.

Conclusion

The common vision of the United Nations to achieve sustainable development by 2030 remains the focus of education stakeholders, in curriculum implementation practices, and education continue to play a cross-cutting role in all the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This paper has thus discussed curriculum pathways and vocational/technical competency-based education for achieving sustainable development goals in education. Curriculum pathways remain both the career paths and the structured programme of studies which determine the preparedness of learners for sustainability in the society. It has been made crystal clear that vocational and

technical education through the many pathways embedded in the field is a viable route to sustainable development.

Also, for learners to acquire the sellable skills and employability skills values embedded in vocational/technical education and training, the core idea of competency-based Education must be integrated within the theories of measurable competency level.. Hence, the practical exposition and interpretations of Competency-Based Education (CBE) were explored to avoid contradictions with a view to achieving vocational/technical competency-based education in the theory and practice of education. It is the candid opinion of the author that, if the systematic development and delivery of instruction to learners are well guided by the philosophical lens of the theories appraised in respect of CBE, along with the application of criterion-referenced assessment discussed in measurable terms, learners would be well prepared for a sustainable world. A call to action is also made for education stakeholders as suggested recommendations to consider from a worthwhile perspective of the subject matter discussed. All put together, would no doubt, boost the vision to achieve sustainable development goals in education and through education as the launch pad.

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